

VIEWPOINT

What is soil biodiversity?

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I received an email from a colleague working on the development of soil-related policies, posing a “simple” question: How do you (scientists) define soil biodiversity? Is there a common definition? That was an unexpected query. It made me think and I realized that the answer is “no.” Although this is an apparently easy question, answers can be as diverse as soil biodiversity. Depending on the respondent (e.g., scientist, policymaker, farmer), definitions of soil biodiversity can vary and can lead to completely different actions in terms of conservation initiatives.

From a preservation point of view, the principle is simple: if you want to protect anything, you need to know what this thing is and be able to monitor it. Policymakers need to know what soil biodiversity is, in order to propose and monitor targeted measures. In this context, the soil biodiversity scientific community still faces two main issues. The first is the lack of indicators and thresholds that can be proposed to policymakers to ensure reliable monitoring and impact assessment schemes. However, on the positive side, over recent years, an initial list of potential indicators has been proposed (Guerra et al., 2021).

The second issue is even more crucial. It relates to the definition of soil biodiversity itself. This definition can directly affect the number and type of monitoring indicators and thresholds. An official and common definition of soil biodiversity is still lacking. Scientists often take a holistic view: we should protect soil as a whole, as a valuable ecosystem, to protect whatever lives in it. Decisionmakers are more pragmatic; they want a list of names of soil organisms to be included in the biodiversity policy agenda. This is what scientists should provide them with.

The issue is far from trivial. For example, about three quarters of all wild bee species nest in the soil and spend

much of their life cycle underground (Antoine & Forrest, 2021). Do we consider wild bees as part of soil biodiversity? Judging by the relevant policies (and common sense), that is not the case. Bees are seen as flying pollinators and are targeted accordingly by policy measures. Current preservation legislation targets the flying stages of pollinators, not the soil stage. However, if we consider wild bees as soil-living organisms, actions for protecting pollinators will also underpin soil organism conservation. Placing protection of soil biodiversity under the umbrella of other initiatives puts it at risks of being too reductive. Due to its major functional significance and diversity, soil life requires specific and targeted measures, and yet it has often been neglected (Cameron et al., 2018).

Over the last few years, the need for actions to protect soil biodiversity has become increasingly relevant at a policy level. The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) has recently published the first-ever global assessment of the status of soil biodiversity (FAO et al., 2020). Authorities are willing to act upon this information. Policy formulators require a clear definition of “soil biodiversity” to be able to develop the required measures and impact assessments for policy evaluation.

Although soil biologists, and ecologists in general, refer to “soil biodiversity” as the community of organisms living in the soil, it is not enough to say that soil biodiversity is whatever organism lives in the soil. For some organisms (such as earthworms), this description is crystal clear—but for others (such as bumblebees nesting in soil), the distinction is blurred. And this is where troubles arise. According to the FAO’s global report: “We define soil biodiversity as the variety of life below ground, from genes and species to the communities they form, as well as the

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ecological complexes to which they contribute and to which they belong, from soil micro-habitats to landscapes.” (FAO et al., 2020). From a political point of view, this definition is vague. Policy development often relies on details and certainty. For instance, how do insects that spend their larval stage in soil and then emerge to live above ground fit into the FAO’s definition? Depending on the answer, the habitats of an endangered species may change including the soil, thus leading to implications for soil management policy. For instance, the design and implementation of a protected area would also take soil into account, which currently is not the case.

Most of the studies available that focus on large-scale distribution and conservation of soil biodiversity consider organisms that are well known to be soil-living (e.g., earthworms). However, a portion of organisms—such as soil-living larvae and vertebrates—are also part of soil biodiversity according to the FAO assessment, but are beyond the radar of current scientific investigations and overall debate on soil biodiversity conservation. There are two possible reasons behind this. First, there is a lack of data on those organisms. However, this is unlikely to be the root cause, as the current facilities and research networks could facilitate data collection. The second, more plausible, reason relates to the definition of soil biodiversity. Common thinking is that soil-living larvae and vertebrates are not part of soil biodiversity. Apart from a few cases of mammals that live their entire life in the soil (e.g., moles and naked mole-rats), most soil vertebrates only spend part of their time in the soil. Think of foxes, badgers, and all those animals (including some birds) that create burrows underground. Should they be considered as soil organisms? According to current conservation policies, the answer is no. However, soil is a key element for their survival. In the long term, this inconsistency has led and will continue to lead to shortcomings in both research and policy development. This is because soil biodiversity scientists have only limited interest in these animals (research gap), and current protection plans for them, where they exist, do not include soil measures (policy gap).

This may appear to be a pointless debate. However, when taking policy initiatives on biodiversity conservation, it is not. In many regions, such as in the European Union, policymakers are willing to start developing plans to protect soil biodiversity. Having a clear definition is the first step toward allowing soil life to enter into the legislative agenda for conservation. Therefore, it is now the time to propose a robust definition for soil biodiversity. When, if ever, are mammals and insects considered as soil organ-

isms? Can we set evidence-based thresholds for defining this? Otherwise, we risk either excluding soil biodiversity from nature conservation, or having blurred definitions established during the legislative process. This will lead to ineffective measures.

There is an urgent need for clarity for the policy side. If the scientific community does not come up with a clear detailed definition, listing all organisms included, soil biodiversity conservation will not take off and momentum will be lost. I, personally, think that a definition of soil biodiversity has to be inclusive. We should adopt the mindset that interaction with soil is a key component of the life of many organisms, and if it were to be removed, the population of those creatures would be significantly impacted. Thus making them part of soil biodiversity. The discussion remains open.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

AO conceived and wrote the paper.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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How to cite this article: Orgiazzi, A. What is soil biodiversity? *Conservation Letters*. 2022;15:e12845. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12845>